

Data Pitch

H2020-ICT-2016-1

Project number: 732506

D7.1 Exploitation Strategy

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Deliverable nature:	Report (R)
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	Public (PU)
Nature	Other
Work package	Sustainability and Exploitation (WP7)
Contractual delivery date:	30th June 2018
Actual delivery date:	30th June 2018
Version:	V1
Keywords:	Exploitation

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1. Executive summary

The Exploitation Strategy has been developed in order to ensure that the Data Pitch programme results are fully mainstreamed, multiplied and sustained. The plan will describe the activities to undertake in order to ensure the continuation of the outputs beyond the life of the programme. There is a huge opportunity to ensure a positive impact on the culture of corporates in sharing data, by the success of the startups within Data Pitch's accelerator.

The goal is to allow others to benefit and be influenced by the programme outputs. This can take form by means of the products and services produced by the startups and SME's, or by providing visibility to the successful use cases of data sharing collaborations that can inspire others to follow suit.

2. Introduction

In order to have a successful exploitation strategy, partners are responsible for ensuring the use of programme results during and after implementation. The consortium must convince stakeholders that the project results are worthy of use. In order emphasis a successful exploitation plan, we must describe the activities needed to be performed in order promote use and adoption of the programme results to guarantee the continuation of Data Pitch outputs beyond it's life.

One aspect of Data Pitch which is unique, is its exploitation potential. The aim of the project is to strengthen the European data sharing economy by bringing together corporate and public-sector organisations that have data with startups and SMEs that work with data. Data Pitch will look to support the members of our partnership program in commercializing their data-centric ideas, some of which will be implemented with financial means offered by the project. Significant efforts are dedicated to allow startups and SMEs to showcase their ideas to potential investors and lay out sustainable exploitation plans and business models. This document will define an exploitation strategy for the main outcomes of the project, including, most relevantly, a plan to ensure the continuity and growth of a data sharing network.

Article 28 of the Data Pitch Grant agreement outlines that each beneficiary must — up to four years after the duration of the programme (36 months) -ensure 'exploitation' of its results by:

- (a) using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- (c) creating and providing a service, or
- (d) using them in standardisation activities.

3. Exploitable Results

3.1. Commercial Results

Data Pitch's main output is the data driven products and services that will result from the startups and SME's within the 2 acceleration phases. The commercial development of the products and services will help the start-ups and SMEs become profitable and provide the EU population with something that they may want or need. Success of these startups will also reflect on the value that can be created from a data sharing economy. By advocating this, Data Pitch will hopefully bring further impact to the EU economy by promoting corporates and public sector organisations to share more data either openly or with startups to foster innovation. Indirectly, the development of new commercial products and services will potentially improve the labour market by creating new jobs within the economy. It is expected that Data Pitch will accelerate up to 50 companies during the duration of the programme, which can potentially have a substantial impact on society.

The stronger the success of these Startups and SME's, the more acknowledgements will be made on the value of sharing data and thus a further increase of future engagement of Corporates sharing data will emerge. As data owners begin to see the benefits to the ecosystem of sharing data collaboratively with startups, the likelihood is that we will see development in a number of sectors such as; Healthcare, Smart Manufacturing, Transport and many more that have been focused on in the programme . Additionally, the programme is looking to highlight the impact in economic terms (money, investments, revenue) that can be generated through a data sharing culture. These expected benefits will help to support the European Commission's decision to fund projects similar to Data Pitch.

3.1.1. Knowledge Results

In order to support the exploitation of shared data, and to promote corporates and public sector organisations to engage with Startups and SME's. Data Pitch will be able to provide a number of knowledge results that will enable collaboration and can help foster innovation. Knowledge results include training material, informational articles, toolkits, webinar recordings and data sharing guidelines, including;

Knowledge producing deliverables include;

- Project fact sheet & internal communication tools
- Online presence and marketing tools
- Legal and privacy toolkit v1
- Training curriculum, learning materials, and webinars
- Data legality report v1
- EaaS facilities and support
- Experiments oversight tools
- Legal and privacy toolkit v2

The exploitation strategy will describe the necessary mechanisms to ensure that the data sharing economy is developed by empowering users to learn from the activities and results produced from Data Pitch.

3.1.2. Network of Data Sharing Organisations

The data pitch model is advocating the use and openness of large corporates and public sector organisations sharing data to foster innovation. By attempting to change organisational culture and policy, the data sharing community will be able to exploit opportunities to work with such data. This emphasis on sharing data can help to remove barriers within certain industries that block collaborative efforts. The output of this movement can have real benefits to the economy, including impacts on societal and environmental challenges.

3.1.3. Accelerator Programme Results

There are a number of exploitable outputs from the Data Pitch accelerator programme that can be used to the benefit of the partners within the consortium. The programme has been specifically tailored to accommodate remote working in a pan European setting. As an data innovation 'lab', Data Pitch will support collaborations between corporations and public sector organisations with startups who are working with shared data. Partners will be able to exploit the Data Pitch innovation programme created both during and after the life of the project, to help support data driven products and services in becoming validated businesses.

During the acceleration period, the startups and SMEs will receive seed funding and acceleration support for a period of 6 months. The program will help exploit the project results by providing training, funding, mentoring and networking to drive commercialization and profitability ensuring sustainability of the funded ideas. This peer to peer support will look to create a stronger possibility of success and impact on the sectors defined in the challenges, as well as the mentality of corporates in promoting data sharing to foster innovation.

The exploitation plan will also highlight the measures to be taken to ensure success in future similar acceleration programmes.

4. Exploitable Results

4.1. Commercial Results

In order for the products and services that are scaled in Data Pitch to become sustainable, there has to be a strong following from corporate and public sector organisations that will benefit and use the outputs produced. The Data Pitch model enables a number of startups to secure future business from working directly with our data providers, to ensure a customised approach to solving their industry challenge. By understanding and providing a solution to this challenge, the Data Pitch model offers a unique way for collaboration and innovation to develop.

Moreover, to ensure support to all startups in scaling and securing business, the consortium proposes to offer high visibility of success stories via the ODI and Beta-i's resources. As an indirect mechanism to ensure use of the product or service, the consortium must also ensure usefulness via the project evaluation. To promote the use of these products and services by end users, the consortium will provide marketing training, toolkits and expert advice to all startups that require development.

4.1.1. Evaluation of project milestones

There will be 2 face to face evaluations of Milestones 2 and 3 that are linked to payments. There will be three main areas covered in the evaluations, including; technical content; implementation, and impact. The technical content revolves around the innovation that have taken place to develop a new service/product through using shared data. Implementation refers to the feasibility and viability of the product/service. Evaluators will analyse its financial viability and take into consideration time constraints of the acceleration period and finally, the Impact that the product/service creates on the defined challenge.

The Evaluators will consist of both internal and external experts to the consortium. Each review will look to include one technical and one non-technical evaluator. The process will first have an initial filter in order to optimize cost and improve efficiencies. The shortlisted candidates will have to pass the more thorough evaluation.

At the end of the support programme we will make sure that the companies get the best start by running demonstration days alongside the final Milestone review, to maximise face to face interaction between the startups themselves, as well as potential investors and clients. This event will allow both partners and startups to exploit Data Pitch's network.

4.1.2. Marketing Plan

The consortium will look to provide marketing support where required. This support will be available in many forms, such as the bespoke marketing and communications support from the ODI, as well as providing access to mentors and advisors with knowledge on how to develop a healthy marketing plan.

The programme will also look to provide training and resources for startups to seek greater traction within the market. These training and resources include workshops such as 'Getting Press' and 'How to get word of mouth for your startup'. In addition to these workshops, online documentation and resources such as the 'marketing toolkit' will be available for all startups to exploit, which includes, but is not limited to;

- Data Pitch logo's
- Data Pitch font's
- Data Pitch slide templates

4.2. Infrastructure Exploitation

4.2.1. User Feedback

To develop usability we will work with the users to find opportunities for improvement. We will do this by encouraging feedback from the startups and SMEs. The feedback will be collected via a formal survey conducted at the end of the acceleration. More direct feedback will be received on 1-2-1 basis with the advisors and recorded within Airtable for record.

4.2.2. Training Material

Training material will be provided to startups and SME's to promote opportunities of knowledge transfers. The training materials will be available through the [Data Innovation Academy](#), via the Data Pitch website. The training materials will cover and look to improve literacy skills in open

data, data science and digital business skills. The training materials provided will combine partner created and curated content from high quality courses available online.

4.3. Knowledge Exploitation

All knowledge developed during Data Pitch will be open for access to any interested party. This includes training documents, toolkits and data-privacy guidelines. Success stories will be featured and advertised on social media sites, as well as through mainstream media and press opportunities.

Data Pitch will further strengthen the benefits of data sharing as a way of creating sustainable impact on the data sharing community. In order to create an online repository enriched with all the knowledge results, the Data Pitch website will endeavor to promote all documentation including; deliverables, training materials, articles and webinars. In order to ensure exploitation of the knowledge results, the ODI and Beta-i will look to provide these resources and learnings to their own startups within their organisational accelerator programmes.

4.4. Acceleration Programme Exploitation

4.4.1. Acceleration Programme

The Data Pitch acceleration programme will be a product that can be utilised to accelerate startup and SME's working with shared data. This product will provide up to 50 startups support, advisorship and mentorship over a 6 month period to help scalability.

The success and use of the acceleration programme will be due to the quality and relevancy of all services provided. In order to enable all the services to be fully utilised and recognised, consortium partners will ensure open accessibility. The programme will also feature control mechanisms such as milestone reviews and bi-weekly reports to track the performance and track engagement with the services.

4.4.2. Data Pitch Acceleration Handbook

The consortium has created a Data Pitch Acceleration Handbook, which is accessible by all. The handbook enables programme participants to understand the services and perks provided to the participants. This document will be reviewed at the end of the first acceleration phase, to determine the services and perks offered to the startups, and to look for improvements or efficiencies in its content. This will also act as guide for future programmes on how remote accelerators can be run.

4.4.3. Kick off Event

The kick off event enabled a forum for all startups, data providers and consortium partners to meet face to face. By making this event a public event, and inviting key figures within the local ecosystem, this event format lends itself to a successful display of how remote acceleration programmes can reduce the barriers and blockers within such programmes. For remote accelerators to work effectively, relationships need to develop. Establishing these at the beginning of the programme will result in future programmes run effectively.

4.4.4. Demonstration Day

The demonstration day offers startups the opportunity to present their products/services to potential clients, customers and investors. By successfully facilitating this event, partners would be able to seek further funding opportunities for startups to become a viable and sustainable

business. Additionally, by running these events and inviting key individuals within the startup landscape, partners are able to expand the reach of the programme through word of mouth and relevant peer networks.

4.5. Data Pitch Network Exploitation

4.5.1. Partnerships

Data Pitch has an ever growing network of partnerships, which includes, entrepreneurs, investors and corporates. By promoting these partnerships and generating connections between parties will encourage the use and power of a support network. It's expected that relationships that emerge between members and partners have potential to impact on the willingness to share data to promote use and innovation within the economy.

4.5.2. DataPitch.Eu

The Data Pitch [website](#) serves as the main dissemination instrument for the programme. The content on the site is constantly iterating and updating to ensure its relevance to our audience. By acting as a centralised location for training, online resources and news, we are able to promote the activities of the programme and expand our reach.

5. Exploitation Plan by Partner

5.1. Beta-i

During the duration of Data Pitch, Beta-i has been assuring the involvement of the program in a series of events aligned with the exploitation of its results. This involvement has different forms with different objectives according to the stage of the program:

1. Prepare - Promote Data Pitch to startups and entrepreneurs. During the 1st year of the program to create awareness and attract startups to apply. Presence at Pixelscamp in 2017.
2. Accelerate - Matchmaking between Data Providers and startups. During the 2nd year of the program to create further engagement between the big data ecosystem stakeholders and leverage the existing relationship from the program participants. Presence at Lisbon Investment Summit in 2018.
3. Share - Disseminate the results of the program and generate discussion around case studies of collaboration between startups and corporate companies. During the 3rd year of the program. Possible presence at Lisbon Investment Summit in 2019 or a similar event.

Additionally, as one of the main European accelerators, during and after the program, Beta-i plans to share the results, case studies and best practices of the program to a wide network of startups, corporate companies and government agencies with the aim of strengthening the data ecosystem in Europe. Having a large experience and portfolio of open innovation programs that create a safe space for corporates and startups to work together, Beta-i is in a privileged position to work as an advocate for data sharing and further utilization of data to create sustainable businesses in Europe.

5.2. Dawex

DAWEX will provide its Global Data Marketplace to ensure the exploitation of the results of Data Pitch. Our marketplace is already operational, with 3,500+ companies exchanging data, across

borders and sectors. It will allow to ensure exploitation and sustainability of the project by giving the opportunity to the data providers and startups who have been part of Data Pitch, to pursue their activity through Dawex: they will be able to find new relevant data sources, to discover potential partners and innovative companies interested in data, and to enable new business models by monetizing their data to other organizations, while retaining full control over the process.

5.3. ODI

The ODI will look to exploit the project results to strengthen its own processes and methodologies in encouraging the data economy in the UK to publish and consume data openly. Furthermore, the ODI will also look to further establish themselves as a hub for open innovation expertise, as validating the Data Pitch model will provide the ODI with an approach in which we can target and exploit specific sector change programmes. By incorporating this model, the ODI will be able to bring more open innovation opportunities to startups and SME's, further strengthening the data economy. In order to realise this opportunity, the ODI will look to expand and exploit it's partner networks through the collaborations with data providers and consortium partners.

5.4. SOTON

SOTON will exploit the project results for both educational and industrial purposes. The exploitation for educational institutes will be mainly targeted at Southampton Business School (SBS), School of Electronics and Computer Science (ECS) and the Southampton Law School

- Data Pitch has presented in the ECS series of lectures on Data Science.
- To promote Data Pitch to industry, SOTON will make full use the Research and Innovation Services (RIS) in SOTON, which has the experience to promote and support the transfer of research expertise and knowledge into industry and maximize the commercial and societal impact;
- Soton has engaged with Future Worlds, the University's on campus start up incubator, about data innovation, and will engage with SetSquared, the enterprise collaboration between the universities of Surrey, Southampton, Bath, Bristol and Exeter;
- Soton has already begun to transfer the knowledge developed in Data Pitch regarding data innovation to other contexts, such as the Interreg 2Seas project 'Smart Cities Innovation Framework Implementation', where it is sharing knowledge on accelerators for the development of innovative market solutions for the public sector challenges of medium sized cities.

IT Innovation Centre

The experience gained in setting up the infrastructure for the experimentation is the main exploitable asset that the IT Innovation Centre is already using in different research and commercial projects and that is going to be further exploited in incoming opportunities.

Within the complex ecosystem present in Data Pitch we have played a major role as technical leaders, contributing to the definition of challenges and later work plans that are at the same time scientifically ambitious and business soundly. This activity has surely increased the knowledge and ability already present in the Centre to be able to discuss, plan and act both at technical and business/commercial level at the same time. This will benefit the typical technology transfer role to bridge the gap between academia and industry the Centre has in its core mission. Moreover, new business opportunities will be generated by the visibility and by the recognized and increased

competence the Centre is gaining by participating in the Data Pitch project.

Institute for the Law and the Web (ILAWS)

The Legal and Privacy Toolkit (“the toolkit”) is a crucial component of the Data Pitch programme; and the main focus of the Institute for the Law and the Web (ILAWS) based at the University of Southampton. In June 2017, the first version of the toolkit was published on the Data Pitch website: <https://datapitch.eu/privacytoolkit/>. The toolkit covers a wide-range of key legal considerations that are likely to occur in the course of an open innovation programme – from contractual obligations to intellectual property rights. Ultimately, the purpose of the toolkit is to provide legal guidance and training to those involved with open innovation acceleration.

Exploitation of the toolkit commenced with contributions to (i) an article and the following conference activities: (ii) a panel discussion at the 10th International Conference on Computers, Privacy & Data Protection - The Age of Intelligent Machines in January 2017; (iii) a panel discussion at the 11th International Conference on Computers, Privacy & Data Protection of Internet Bodies in January 2018; and (iv) a conference presentation at the IAPP European Data Protection Intensive Conference in April 2018.^[1] It is anticipated that during the course of the Data Pitch programme, the toolkit will facilitate further dissemination activities.

In the longer-term, it is hoped that the pragmatic nature of the toolkit will help to provide a springboard for future legal research within open innovation by bringing together an understanding of the key legal issues that occur in practice with those theoretical legal issues explored as part of the literature.

[1] See the following for further information: (i) Hu, Runshan and Stalla-Bourdillon, Sophie and Yang, Mu and Schiavo, Valeria and Sassone, Vladimiro, Bridging Policy, Regulation, and Practice? A Techno-Legal Analysis of Three Types of Data in the GDPR (September 1, 2017). in 'Data Protection and Privacy: The Age of Intelligent Machines' Edited by Ronald Leenes Rosamunde van Brakel, Serge Gutwirth and Paul De Hert, Hart Publishing, 2017. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3034261> ; (ii) Panel Discussion on: “The Law and Science of De-identification” organised by the Future of Privacy Forum (Dr. Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon was a panel member), 10th International Conference on Computers, Privacy & Data Protection - The Age of Intelligent Machines, 25-27 January 2017, Brussels, Belgium (p. 29) <http://www.cpdpconferences.org/assets/cdp2017.pdf> [last accessed 8 June 2018]; (iii) Panel Discussion on: “Data Protection and Innovation Acceleration” organised by Data Pitch, 11th International Conference on Computers, Privacy & Data Protection - The Internet of Bodies, 24-26 January 2018, Brussels, Belgium, (p. 26) http://www.cpdpconferences.org/assets/CPDP2018_PROGRAM_FINAL.pdf [last accessed 1 June 2018]; and, (iv) Alison Knight and Gary LaFever, “Just Because You’re GDPR Compliant Does Not Mean You Can Use Your Data”, IAPP European Data Protection Intensive Conference 2018, 18 April 2018 at: <https://iapp.org/conference/iapp-europe-data-protection-intensive-2018/sessions-dpi18/?id=a191a00001JieyAAC> [last accessed 1 June 2018].